

CRYOGENIC GRINDING OF SPICES IS A NOVEL APPROACH WHEREAS AMBIENT GRINDING NEEDS IMPROVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Study on ambient and cryogenic grinding was performed to test the novelty of cryogenic grinding and pin point the drawbacks of ambient grinding. Comparative study had shown that ambient grinding need more power (8.92%) and specific energy (14.5%) than cryogenic grinding. Particle size analysis had shown that cryogenic grinding produced coarser particles. Comparative study of energy law constant shows that ambient is more power consumptive. The higher amount of volatile oil (2.15 ml/100 g) content was found in cryogenic grinding and also powder of freshness and lower whiteness (40%) and higher yellowness (14%) indices found for cryogenic grinding.

KEYWORDS: Ambient, cryogenic, grinding, volatile oil, mill, particle, diameter, power, specific energy.

INTRODUCTION

Grinding is an important unit operation in which the size of the particle is reduced and their surface area is increased. When increasing surface area of particles, it means the availability of constituents (such as oil inside the cells, fragrance and flavouring components) that are available in the material is increases. Power consumption in grinding, size of the commented particles and increase in the surface area depends on the initial size, shape and strength of the particle or material; the kind of grinder or mill used for this unit operation and the fixing of operating parameter to running the grinder or mill such as temperature, size of sieve, number of rotor ribs, etc (Das, 2005).

Grinding is the most power consuming operation because only 1% of the energy imparted into the material is utilized loosening the bond between particles, whereas almost 99% of input energy is dissipated as heat, rising the temperature of the ground product etc. In spice grinding temperature rises to the extent of 42 - 93°C (Singh and Goswami, 1997) and this causes the loss of volatile oil and flavouring constituents; for high oil bearing material, oil comes out from oil bearing material during grinding, which makes ground product gummy, sticky and results in chocking of sieves through which the product passes (Singh and Goswami, 1997).

Thermal damage is one of the main limitations of the conventional grinding process, so it is especially important to perform the grinding under controlled temperatures conditions. Calculation of temperature and its effect on thermal damage to the material undergoing grinding was carried out by Malkin and Guo (2007) and suggest that if we can reduce the temperature of two rubbing surfaces, we can obtain better product.

The fundamental principle of cryogenic grinding is similar to that of conventional grinding methods for materials, but the compositions are very complex, containing aromatics of high volatility, oils and fats, which are easily oxidized. Using liquid nitrogen or liquid air as the cryogen, all of thermo-sensitive herbal medicines, spices and important food commodity can be ground below their brittle temperature. The colour and other properties of the products of cryogenic grinding will not be changed and their flavour and nutritional value will not be lost (Shimo *et al.*,1991). The usefulness of cryogenic grinding can be summed up as (1) the conventional or ambient grinding of spices results in inferior quality of the product having several operational problems such dust formation. (2) the application of cryogenic

technology for grinding of spices has been scientifically proved to be suitable technique with less loss of volatile oil content, improved colour and grinding operation. (3) the research information and data generated on properties of spices and cryogenic grinding would help to understand grinding phenomena and develop efficient grinding system. Cryogenic grinding produced Gelucire 44/14 in a powder form and did not change its physical properties, emulsification capacities and dissolution performances of the formulation (Chambin *et al.*, 2004). The normal grinding produces poor quality of powder that does not conform to the international quality standard; as a result either fetches lower prices or not accepted by the importer countries. The temperature rise of the product can be minimized to some extent by circulating cold air or water around the grinder. But this technique is not sufficient enough to significantly reduce the temperature rise of the product. The loss of volatile can be significantly reduced by the cryogenic grinding technique using liquid nitrogen or liquid carbon dioxide that provides the refrigeration needed to pre-cool the spices and maintain the desired low temperature by absorbing heat generation during grinding operation. The extremely low temperature in the grinder solidifies the oil so that the spices become brittle, they crumble easily permitting grinding to a finer and more consistent size. The high quality ground product would have domestic as well as international market. There is need for modelling of grinding process (Stepien, 2009). Limited research information is available on the cryogenic grinding of spices. The present study was undertaken with the objectives of comparative study on power and specific energy requirement for ambient and cryogenic grinding of black pepper; study of different energy law constants; effect of ambient and cryogenic grinding on particle size; volatile oil content and colour retention.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample preparation

For the present investigation, black pepper was collected from Indian Institute of Spices Research (IISR), Calicut, Kerala, India during May 2009. The pepper were cleaned manually to separate out the stones, dirt, dust, broken, foreign, unwanted matters and immature seeds from the main sample of black pepper. The initial moisture content (mc) and mc after grinding of the black pepper on dry basis (db), was determined by oven drying method at 72°C for 24 h until a constant weight was obtained (Ranganna, 1995).

$$Q = \frac{W_i(M_f - M_i)}{100 - M_f}$$

(1)

where, Q is amount of water to be added in ml, W_i is initial mass of sample (g), M_i is initial mc (% db), M_f is final mc (% db). The pepper was kept in sealed and moisture resistant flexible polyethylene bags.

Ambient and Cryogenic Grinding

Rotor mill

Rotor mill (Model Pulverisette 14, Fritsch, Germany) is one of the types among the several types of size reduction devices were used for ambient and cryogenic grinding. In this device the size reduction of particle takes place by impacts of the rotating ribs and attrition of the particle on sieve and mill's stationary surfaces. The peripheral speed of the rotors ranges between 70 (15000 RPM) to 90 (20000 RPM) m s⁻¹. The major components of the mill are rotor (88.5 mm dia.) having 8 to 12 number of fixed ribs, sieve rings of different opening sizes (0.08, 0.12, 0.2, 0.5 and 1.0 mm) are available and 1 and 0.5 mm sieves are used for present study. The speed of rotor could be controlled through an in built mechanism.

Experimental procedure

The experiment for ambient grinding was carried out at room temperature. First of all cleaned and sieved sample was made ready for grinding, grinder was switched on, sample was fed manually into the feed hopper slowly to avoid chocking of sieve and product was obtained at collector pan from an outlet. Similarly, in cryogenic grinding Liquid nitrogen (LN₂) was fed along with the sample and ground product was obtained at collector pan from an outlet. A temperature indicator, 600 to -200°C (Testo, Germany) was inserted into the outlet of powder to record the temperature of the product.

Size reduction theory in relation to black pepper grinding

Black pepper is a seed and it can't be used as such. It has to be ground for consumption purposes. Grinding also helps in separation of various ingredients of black pepper. The size reduction theory of black pepper involves particle size measurement, particle size analysis, power consumption in grinding (Geankoplis, 2004) etc. Different laws which explain energy requirement in grinding are described in the following sub sections:

Power Requirement in Ambient and Cryogenic Grinding

In size reduction mechanical actions are required to reduce the particles into smaller ones. There is need of energy to fracture and creating new surfaces. Approximate calculations give actual efficiencies of about 0.1 to 2% (Geankoplis, 2004). Theories were derived depending upon the assumption that the energy E required to produce a change dD in a particle of size D in a power function of D .

$$\frac{dE}{dD} = - \frac{C}{D^n} \tag{2}$$

where, D is the diameter of particle in mm, n and C are constants.

A single phase wattmeter (range 0 - 750 W, least count 5 W) was connected with the machine to measure the power consumed and ultimately to measure the energy required in grinding. Mill was run empty and by using stop watch, number of revolutions (m) completed by the energy meter in time ' t_m ' (s) was recorded. Similarly, the total number of revolutions completed (n) to grind the whole sample in time ' t_n ' (s) was also recorded. Power under load was measured at each set of experiments. The circular panel of energy meter was divided into 10 large divisions, each large division had 10 intermediate divisions and each intermediate division was divided into 2 small divisions. So, disc had 200 small divisions. Thus, 1 kWh and 60 revolutions will correspond to 12,000 divisions.

$$\begin{aligned} 1 \text{ division} &= \frac{1}{12000} \text{ kWh} \\ \text{Power consumption} &= \left[\frac{n}{t_n} - \frac{m}{t_m} \right] \times \frac{3600}{12000 \text{ s}} \times \text{kWs} \\ &= 0.3 \left[\frac{n}{t_n} - \frac{m}{t_m} \right] \text{ kW} \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Specific Energy Consumption

It is the amount of energy required to grind the unit amount of material in unit time. It may be expressed in kW kg⁻¹ or kJ kg⁻¹. The following formula was used to calculate the specific energy consumed in grinding (Singh & Goswami, 1997).

$$\text{Specific energy consumption} \left(\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kg}} \right) = \frac{\text{Power consumed (W)} \times 3.6}{\text{Feed rate} \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{h}} \right)} \tag{4}$$

Energy constants

a). Rittenger's law constants (K_r):

Rittinger proposed a law which states that the work in crushing is proportional to the new surface created. From equation (2) it turns to be-

$$E = K_r \left[\frac{1}{D_P} - \frac{1}{D_F} \right] \tag{5}$$

where, D_F is the diameter of feed, D_P is the diameter of product, E is the amount of work required to reduce a unit mass of feed from D_F to D_P and K_r is a constant. This law implies that the same amount of energy is required to reduce a material from 100 to 50 mm as is required to reduce the same material from 50 to 33.33 mm. It has been found experimentally that this law has some validity in grinding fine powders (Geankoplis, 2004).

b). Kick's law constants (K_k):

Kick's law states that energy required to reduce a material in size was directly proportional to the size-reduction ratio. This implies that $n = 1$ in eq (2) and this can mathematically be expressed as follows:

$$E = C \ln \left[\frac{D_F}{D_P} \right]$$

$$E = K_k \ln \left[\frac{D_F}{D_P} \right] \quad (6)$$

where, K_k is a constant. This law implies that the same amount of energy is required to reduce a material from 100 to 50 mm as is needed to reduce the same material from 50 to 25 mm (Singh & Sahay, 2004 & Geankoplis, 2004).

c). Bond's law constants (K_b):

This law states that the work required using a large-size feed is proportional to the square root of the surface/volume ratio of the product. This corresponds to $n = 1.5$ and mathematically this can be expressed as given below (Singh & Sahay, 2004 & Geankoplis, 2004).

$$E = K_b \sqrt{\frac{1}{D_P}}$$

$$E = \frac{P}{\Phi} = K_b \left[\sqrt{\frac{1}{D_P}} - \sqrt{\frac{1}{D_F}} \right] \quad (7)$$

d). Rosin Rammler Sperling Bennet (RRSB) constant

$$\Phi = \exp[-(D/M)^l] \quad (8)$$

where,

$$\Phi = \frac{\text{Cumulative weight of comminuted particles retained on a sieve of size } D}{\text{Net weight of comminuted particles}} \quad (9)$$

D is the sieve size (m), M and l are constants

Particle size analysis

Black pepper seed were ground by using 1 and 0.5 mm size sieve. Particle size analysis of ground spice powder were carried out by using shaker setup and then calculating different diameter. Mass Mean Diameter (MMD): It can be defined as the ratio of mass fraction in individual increment to the total mass fraction together (McCabe *et al.*, 2000).

$$\text{MMD } \mu\text{m} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \Delta \phi_i D}{\sum_{i=1}^n \Delta \phi_i} \quad (10)$$

Volume Surface Mean Diameter (VSMD) or Sauter Mean Diameter (D_s): It can be defined as the 6 times the ratio of volume of 1 kg ground particle (which are assumed to be spherical) and its surface area (Das, 2005). The value of D_s can be estimated from the Eq. (11).

$$D_s \mu\text{m} = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{\Delta\phi_i}{D} \right]} \quad (11)$$

The arithmetic mean diameter (AMD) usually termed as the mean diameter, is the arithmetic average particle diameter of the distribution. The value of the arithmetic mean is sensitive to the quantities of particulate matter at the extreme lower and upper ends of the distribution. It can be mathematically be expressed as Eq. (12)

$$\text{AMD } \mu\text{m} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\Delta\phi_i}{D^2}}{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\Delta\phi_i}{D^3}} \quad (12)$$

Volume Mean Diameter (VMD): It is the ratio of the volume of total mass based on average diameter of total particle to the sum of the volume of each fraction.

$$\text{VMD } \mu\text{m} = \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\Delta\phi_i}{D} \right)^3}{\sum_{i=1}^n \Delta\phi_i} \right]^{0.33} \quad (13)$$

D_{mode} : The mode represents the value that occurs most frequently in a distribution. In particle size distributions, the mode is the particle diameter that occurs most frequently. D_{median} : It is the sieve size in mm or μm through 50% ground material passes out. D_{80} : It the sieve size in mm or μm through which 80% ground material passes. It also helps to know about the extent of fineness obtained by grinding (McCabe *et al.*, 2000), (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Showing D_{mode} , D_{median} and D_{80}

Initial Surface Area (A_i , $m^2 kg^{-1}$) of black pepper seed before grinding can be estimated using the Eq. (14)

$$A_i = \frac{6(1/\rho)}{\psi_i D_i} \quad (14)$$

where, D_i is diameter of pepper before grinding in m, ψ_i is sphericity of pepper before grinding. Total Surface Area (A_t , $m^2 kg^{-1}$) created by Grinding can be obtained using Eq. (15)

$$A_t = \int_0^1 \frac{6 d\phi}{\rho D} = \frac{6}{\rho \psi_o D_s} \quad (15)$$

where, D_s is sauter mean diameter in m, ψ_o is sphericity of pepper after grinding (Das, 2005).

Fineness Modulus (FM): It is an empirical factor obtained by adding the total percentages of a sample of the aggregate retained on each of a specified series of sieves and dividing the sum by 100. This concept helps to describe particle-size distributions by an index number. Many agencies use fineness modulus variation as a convenient means of keeping quality history data on uniformity of particle-size distribution of aggregate production, delivery, and use. Some agencies require that aggregates be processed to remain within upper and lower limits of fineness modulus. Such requirements are more frequently applicable to fine particles.

$$FM = \frac{\text{Total percent retained on sieve}}{100} \quad (16)$$

Quality attributes of spice powder

Volatile oil

Interest in the production of high-quality spice products has encouraged scientists to investigate the effects of cryogenic milling/grinding on spice quality. Ambient and cryogenically milled spices were studied for volatiles oil content retention. Oil was extracted from ambient and cryogenic ground samples by steam distillation method (Masango, 2005; Li *et al.*, 2009).

Colour

The colour is an important quality attributes to accept or reject the spices because it has direct appealing effect in the mind of consumer. For the colour determination purpose chromameter (CR-400/410, Konica Minolta, Tokyo, Japan) was used, which gave L, a and b value, where L value varies between 0 and 100. A perfectly white body has L=100 and a black body has L = 0. A positive value of 'a' indicates the redness and negative value greenness. A positive value of 'b' indicates yellowness and negative value of b shows blueness.

In standard colour chart, at centre a and b zero and they shows gray colour (Das, 2005). For whiteness index (WI) determinations following relations are used.

$$\text{Yellowness (Y)} = L^2/100 \quad (17)$$

$$Z = 1.18103L (L/100 - b/70) \quad (18)$$

$$WI = 3.388Z - 3Y \quad (19)$$

$$YI = 142.86b/L \quad (20)$$

Aroma and fragrance

Aroma and fragrance was just observed by human smelling sense but for better understanding and to know the change in chemical constitute we have to go for Gas chromatographic analysis.

Liquid nitrogen (LN₂) requirement

LN₂ was obtained from Cryogenic Engineering Centre (IIT Kharagpur) @ Rs. 15/ litre. The amount of LN₂ required for grinding was estimated by filling the known amount of LN₂ in Dewar before grinding and then measuring the left LN₂ after grinding in Dewar.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ambient and Cryogenic Grinding

Power consumption (*P*)

Power is the time rate at which work is done or energy is transferred. In calculus terms, power is the derivative of work with respect to time. Ambient and cryogenic grinding was carried out by using rotor speed mill with 0.5 mm and 1 mm sieve opening size. Data such as material taken for grinding and results obtained like product, time taken for grinding, rps, feed rate, power consumption and specific energy are tabulated in Table 1. It is clear from Table 1 that ambient grinding needs more power for grinding compare to cryogenic grinding. It is because during cryogenic grinding material become more brittle. On the contrary, in ambient grinding oil will come out of the cells and make the material sticky in nature and material sticks on the grinding surface which require more amount of power to grind the material.

Table 1 Sieve size, moisture content, grinding time, grinding temperature, feed rate, revolution, power consumption, and specific energy

Factor	Ambient Grinding				Cryogenic Grinding					
	AG ₁		AG ₂		CG ₁		CG ₂		CG ₃	
Sample	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5
Sieve size (mm)	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5
Feed (g)	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200
Feed mc (% db)	11.3	11.2	11.4	11.3	11.3	11.3	11.2	11.4	11.2	11.4
Time taken for grinding (s)	300	332	298	330	286	289	278	280	275	278
Product obtained (g)	199	199	198	199	199	199	198	199	199	199
Product mc (% db)	9.5	9.4	9.4	9.4	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.4	9.4	9.5
Product temperature (°C)	60	64	62	66	-80	-78	-90	-89	-	-108
Revolution in energy meter	119	134	116	133	112	116	105	107	98	102
Feed rate (kg h ⁻¹)	2.4	2.17	2.42	2.18	2.5	2.5	2.56	2.56	2.6	2.58
Power consumption (W)	72	74.2	70	72	68	70	66	67.8	60	63
Specific energy (kJ kg ⁻¹)	110	120	106	115	101	106	93	95.3	83	88

AG = Ambient grinding; CG = Cryogenic grinding

The data are expressed as mean and the coefficient of variation was <5%.

Fig. 2 shows variations in specific energy requirement with variations in grinding temperature.

Fig. 2 Variation in power requirement with varying temperature
 ■ 0.5 mm opening sieve ▲ 1 mm opening sieve

Eq. (21) and (22) shows the variation in power consumption with different temperature while grinding with 1 and 0.5 mm opening sieve size.

1 mm opening sieve

$$P = 76.45 - 0.01T - 0.001T^2 \quad (R^2 = 0.949) \quad (21)$$

0.5 mm opening sieve

$$P = 77.36 + 0.003T - 0.001T^2 \quad (R^2 = 0.941) \quad (22)$$

Specific Energy Requirement (E_s)

Fig. 3 shows variations in specific energy requirement with variations in grinding temperature.

Fig. 3 Variation in specific energy requirement with varying temperature
 ■ 0.5 mm opening sieve ▲ 1 mm opening sieve

Eq. (23) and (24) shows the variation in specific energy with different temperature while grinding with 1 and 0.5 mm opening sieve size.

1 mm opening sieve

$$E_s = 118.3 + 0.012T - 0.002T^2 \quad (R^2 = 0.954) \quad (23)$$

At 0.5 mm opening sieve

$$E_s = 123.2 + 0.060T - 0.002T^2 \quad (R^2 = 0.944) \quad (24)$$

Energy Constant

It is another way to know the amount of power required to grind the material. Table 2 shows Rittenger's, Kick's and Bond's law constants value.

Table 2 Rittenger's, Kick's and Bond's law constants value

Parameter	Ambient Grinding				Cryogenic Grinding					
	AG ₁		AG ₂		CG ₁		CG ₂		CG ₃	
Sample	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5
Sieve size (mm)	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5
K_r (W h mm kg ⁻¹)	16.89	12.79	18.88	14.2	15.87	12.34	13.78	10.87	11.89	9.88
K_k (W h kg ⁻¹)	14	11.97	12.39	12.03	13.04	12.09	13	10.77	9.48	8.70
K_b (W h mm ^{0.5} kg ⁻¹)	26.78	29.8	28.85	29.18	27.96	27.17	26.17	24.26	21.50	17.58

The data are expressed as mean and the coefficient of variation was <5%.

Particle Size Analysis

Table 3 shows the different diameter calculated for the material ground under ambient and cryogenic grinding. It shows true density, initial specific surface and final specific surface area of the sample and its ground powder. It is evident from the table that cryogenic grinding produces fine particles. The mass mean diameter of the cryogenically ground powder was lies between 248 μm (0.25mm) to 502 μm (0.50mm) (Table 3). A low feed rate could produces with low average particle sizes (Indira, 2006).

Table 3 Different types of diameter, specific area before and after grinding

Factor	Ambient Grinding				Cryogenic Grinding					
	AG ₁		AG ₂		CG ₁		CG ₂		CG ₃	
Sample	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5
Sieve size (mm)	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5
D_i , mm	4.89	4.87	4.78	4.87	4.88	4.86	4.98	4.91	4.9	4.89
D_{mode} (μm)	300	210	300	220	400	200	300	205	410	200
D_{median} (μm)	280	210	270	215	400	290	420	280	405	240
D_{80} (μm)	480	280	470	290	510	420	610	420	430	295
MMD (μm)	316	235	226	215	370	301	377	309	450	276
VSMD (μm)	276	188	227	192	435	335	359	270	674	221
AMD (μm)	121	82	112	90	282	144	106	146	358	88
VMD (μm)	261	179	215	182	409	316	338	255	631	210
FM	7.1	7.2	6.9	7.12	6.9	7.32	6.93	7.4	6.94	7.3
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	1200	1200	1200	1200	1200	1200	1200	1200	120	1200
A_i (m ² kg ⁻¹)	1.04	1.05	1.07	1.05	1.05	1.05	1.03	1.04	1.04	1.04
A_f (m ² kg ⁻¹)	20	27	22	26	12	15	14	19	16	21

The data are expressed as mean and the coefficient of variation was <5%.

Volatile oil content

Interest in the production of high-quality spice products has encouraged by scientists to investigate the effects of cryogenic milling on spice quality. Results indicated that cryogenically milled spices retained more of the volatiles of the natural spice. The volatile oil content in cryogenically ground powder varied between 1.98 to 2.15 ml/100 g of powder at -60 to -110 °C (Table 2) respectively. Whereas, in ambient grinding oil was obtained 0.87 to 0.96 ml/100g at 60 to 65 °C product temperature (Fig. 4). Thus, cryogenic grinding helps to avoid the loss of volatile oil of the spice that also helps in retaining aroma and medicinal value of product.

Fig. 4. Volatile oil content obtained from ambient and cryogenically ground sample

Colour

Colour value and colour indexes results of the ambient and cryogenically ground black pepper powder. It can be observed that cryogenic grinding has improved the whiteness and yellowness indexes (Fig. 5), whereas ambient grinding produces ash coloured powder with high whiteness and low yellowness indices thus cryogenic grinding produces improved colour of spice.

Fig. 5. Colour indices for ambient and cryogenically ground sample

Whiteness index

Yellowness index

Liquid nitrogen requirement for cryogenic grinding

LN₂ obtaining and storage is need very careful attention. We can't totally sealed the LN₂ because it starts at boiling -192°C and continuously evaporates from the vessel. So has as soon brought the LN₂ to from central plant used it to avoid losses. The requirement of LN₂ for cryogenic grinding at different very low temperature is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Liquid nitrogen requirement at different cryogenic grinding temperature

It was observed that as we carried out grinding towards more and more negative temperature LN₂ requirement increased and it is represented in eq. (25)

$$LN_2 = 0.828 + 0.007T + 0.0007T^2 \quad (R^2 = 0.992) \quad (25)$$

Comparison between cryogenic and ambient grinding

Power requirement

Ambient grinding needs more power to grind the commodity compare to cryogenic grinding (Fig. 2) it is due to that in ambient for high oil bearing material, oil comes out from oil bearing material during grinding at high temperature (40 to 90 °C) which makes ground product gummy and sticky; gummy powder sticks on grinding surfaces that results in high power consumption and also chocking of sieves through which the product passes.

Specific energy requirement

In case of ambient grinding specific energy consumption was high compare to cryogenic grinding. In ambient grinding at high temperature (40 to 90 °C) oil comes out of cells and makes the product viscous and sticky in nature. This leads to high consumption of power in ambient grinding while in case of cryogenic grinding due to low temperature (-60 to -110 °C) material becomes brittle and frugal in nature and requires less amount of energy for grinding (Fig. 3) (Ghorbani et al., 2010).

Energy constant

It is evident from Table 3 that cryogenic grinding need less power for grinding of commodity compare to ambient grinding.

Particle size of powder

The mass mean diameter in the case of ambient and cryogenic grinding were 326 µm (0.326) to 352 µm (0.352 mm) and 276 µm (0.276 mm) to 202 µm (0.202 mm) which shows that cryogenic grinding produces fine particles compare to ambient grinding (Santos *et al.*, 2002). It was observed that size of product particle is function of feed rate, product temperature and moisture content of the sample.

Colour indexes

In case of ambient grinding due to high production temperature powder turns into dull in colour, became ash like in colour and lost its brightness. On the hand, in cryogenic grinding, high colour indexes were obtained due to preservation of brightness and natural lust of powder.

Yield of volatile oil

A significant difference was observed in yield of volatile from ambient and cryogenic grinding. The yield of volatile oil in cryogenic grinding was obtained in the range of 1.98 to 2.15 ml/100g whereas in ambient grinding it was obtained in the range of 0.87 to 0.96 ml/100g of pepper powder.

Sieve clogging

Sieve clogging is shown in Fig. 7. It is clear from the figure that as the temperature of grinding decreases the clogging of the sieve decreases for the same sieve opening.

Fig. 7 Sieve chocking characteristics in ambient and cryogenic grinding

Health and hygienic condition

A significant loss of volatile oil in ambient grinding may be because of high-grinding temperature that leads to vapourisation of volatile compounds. These fine vaporised oils molecules and spreading of very fine spice powder in surrounding causes eye, nose and throat irritations if inhaled, thereby leading to fatigue of workers. The dust and volatile oil produced during ambient grinding in working atmosphere of worker or mill operator can create respiratory problems (Murthy *et al.*, 1999). Some time, there may fire accident in ambient grinding due to high operating temperature. Eye burning, sneezing and nose watering are common problem arise due to ambient grinding. During cryogenic grinding, the vapourisation of oils was found minimum as most of the oil compounds are retained within the powder itself because of low temperatures, and the oils are present mostly as solid. The dust formation is also very insignificant and the problem of eye burning, sneezing and nose watering are not observed in cryogenic grinding. Such positive aspects of cryogenic grinding show the practical usefulness of this novel technology.

CONCLUSION

It is concluded from study that less specific energy and power were required for cryogenic grinding; improved colour powder was obtained from cryogenic grinding; higher volatile oil content was obtained from cryogenic grinding; clogging of sieve was found to be serious in ambient grinding. LN_2 requirement varied between 1 to 1.4 kg kg^{-1} for grinding temperature of -60 to -110°C . Cryogenic grinding is free from eye burning, sneezing and nose watering and it is a hygienically novel technique.

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